

A Latin American graduate school - The PPGCosmo experience

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on behalf of the PPGCosmo working team *

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General: This contribution describes the PPGCosmo (Programa de Pós-graduação em Astrofísica, Cosmologia e Gravitação) initiative. It is a new and special thematic PhD program based at the Federal University of Espírito Santo (UFES), Brazil, and it is associated to other nine institutions worldwide. The Program started its activities on 2016.

The research topics range from theoretical to observational aspects of Astrophysics, Cosmology and Gravitation, including participation in large collaborations such as Euclid, J-PAS, DES and LIGO-Virgo. Thematic areas include: Dark Matter, Astroparticle Physics, Cosmology, Gravitational Waves, Dark Energy, High Energy Theory, Astronomy and Astrophysics.

Students are from the beginning of their courses associated to an advisor at Brazil and a co-advisor outside Brazil. Given the PPGCosmo example we discuss how a similar graduate school can be implemented to join Latin American research groups on the thematic areas cited above. Such initiative can effectively propel scientific collaborations in the Continent.

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Description of PPGCosmo: Graduate programs in Brazil are usually named by the acronym PPG (Programa de Pós-Graduação). Each PPG, let us take the example of Physics, is based on a certain Faculty of Physics and it offers research areas accordingly to the profile of the researchers of that institution. Contrarily to this usual standard, PPGCosmo is a thematic graduate program which involves researchers from 6 different Brazilian institutions in association with 4 international research groups (see details in <https://ppgcosmo.cosmo.ufes.org>).

Students are accepted after a careful selection process which involves the analysis of CVs, projects, reference letters and that also includes an interview. Every selection process so far had candidates from different continents. Once accepted, students should start their research project at UFES but their mobility between associate institutes is highly encouraged. Theses should be written in English, that is also the language of their public defenses. By 2020 the first accepted students are about to finish their thesis.

The Associate Institutions in Brazil are:

- Brazilian Centre for Research in Physics (CBPF, Brazil)
- Federal University of Bahia (UFBA, Brazil)
- Federal University of Espírito Santo (UFES, Brazil) - Main institute
- Federal University of Juiz de Fora (UFJF, Brazil)
- Federal University of Ouro Preto (UFOP, Brazil)
- International Institute of Physics (IIP, Brazil),

The list of Faculty Members in Brazil is:

- Humberto Belich (UFES)
- Saulo Carneiro (UFBA)
- Marc Casals (CBPF)
- Júlio C. Fabris (UFES)
- Wiliam Hipólito-Ricaldi (UFES)
- Martin Makler (CBPF)
- Valerio Marra (UFES)
- Oliver F. Piattella (UFES)
- Nelson Pinto-Neto (CBPF)
- Davi C. Rodrigues (UFES)

- Ilya Shapiro (UFJF)
- Riccardo Sturani (IIP)
- Felipe T. Falciano (CBPF)
- Hermano Velten (UFOP)

During the PhD project the students take part in a one-year internship at one of the research groups led by the following collaborators abroad:

- Luca Amendola (Heidelberg University - Germany)
- Scott Dodelson (Carnegie Mellon University - USA)
- José de Freitas Pacheco (Côte d’Azur Observatory, OCA - France)
- David Wands (Portsmouth University - UK)

Perspectives for a Latin American graduate school

The activities in observational Astrophysics and Cosmology in Latin America have increased considerably mainly due to the construction of observatories in Chile, but also in Argentina. These observatories are among the best scientific facilities in the world at this moment. Even if the financial budget for their constructions came mainly from US and Europe, there is also an important effort of the Latin American countries.

However, the participation of many Latin American countries in these projects is below what could be expected. In this sense, a graduate program in Astrophysics and Cosmology, in the form of a network, may allow to propagate the formation of Latin American scientists in those domains. This graduate program may follow closely the PPGCosmo format, with the participation of universities and scientific institutions of different Latin American countries. The students of this program could have e.g. two co-advisors of different countries, increasing the scientific cooperation between the involved institutions.

The student formation could cover theoretical aspects of Astrophysics and Cosmology, but a preference would be given to observational/experimental formation, with the intensive use of the astronomical facilities installed in the Continent.

One important aspect, borrowing the PPGCosmo initiative, is that the formation of the student, even if done mainly at a given institution, must include a internship period in other institution belonging to the network, allowing the integration of the Latin American community working in Astrophysics and Cosmology. The use of the astronomical/experimental structures installed in the South of the Continent would be a priority in the PhD network program.